

1 **Soil carbon and nutrients (N, P, and K) content in the tropical shifting cultivation system**
2 **under Indigenous agricultural management practices - A review**

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24 **Abstract**

25 Farmers largely depend on the soil's natural fertility in the shifting cultivation system, using
26 minimal or no external agricultural inputs, and rely on slash-and-burn to clear fields due to limited
27 resources. This system follows a cycle involving conversion, cultivation, and restoration phases,
28 where various indigenous practices are applied, influencing soil nutrient dynamics positively and
29 negatively. Significant efforts have been made to examine the relationship between soil organic
30 carbon, nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium), and indigenous agricultural practices in
31 tropical shifting cultivation. The findings from these studies need to be assessed to improve
32 understanding and better inform decision-making. This review consolidates these results,
33 emphasizing the status, similarities, controversies, and knowledge gaps. Overall, practices in
34 shifting cultivation tend to have long-term negative impacts on soil fertility, requiring an extended
35 recovery period. Unfortunately, tropical lands are experiencing shortening fallow periods.
36 However, agroforestry has been identified as an alternative to enhance the resilience of affected
37 lands offering additional benefits for soil fertility. Crop rotation, mixed cropping, minimum tillage,
38 cover crops, and incorporating crop residues can also improve soil fertility by increasing soil
39 organic carbon and nutrient levels. Therefore, promoting knowledge exchange with indigenous
40 farmers can contribute to more agroecological resilient farming systems.

41 **Keywords:** Indigenous farmers, shifting cultivation, soil carbon, soil nutrient, tropical lands,
42 agricultural sustainability

43 1. Introduction

44 Soil carbon (C), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K) are widely recognized as key
45 indicators of soil quality (Mishra et al. 2024). Recent scientific efforts have focused on
46 establishing soil quality indicators, highlighting soil C, N, P, and K contents as the most commonly
47 measured parameters (Pavlu et al. 2021). In recent years, the impact of Indigenous agricultural
48 management practices (IAMPs) on soil C and nutrients (N, P, AND K) in tropical regions has
49 become a major concern (Purwanto and Alam 2020). The choice of IAMPs is conditioned by rapid
50 population growth, financial constraints, and limited agricultural knowledge (File and Nhamo
51 2023). The growing population living in poverty has increased reliance on extensive farming
52 practices, which primarily depend on the soil's natural fertility (Mugizi and Matsumoto 2020).
53 Global population projections indicate a rise to 9.9 billion by 2050 and 25 billion by the end of the
54 21st century (Cleland 2013), while others forecast continued growth to 10.9 billion by 2100
55 (Forman and Wu 2016). Efforts to boost food production to meet the needs of this expanding
56 population, often with limited agricultural inputs, contribute to further land degradation. As a
57 result, indigenous farming systems increasingly damage the ecosystem (Yang et al. 2020),
58 resulting in low yields (Anderson et al. 2020). The decreasing yield is primarily driven by the loss
59 of soil fertility, caused by changes in soil properties such as the depletion of soil organic matter
60 (SOM), essential plant nutrients, and the deterioration of soil aggregation (Mutuku et al. 2021). In
61 the absence of external inputs, studies have shown that certain IAMPs such as agroforestry,
62 fallowing, mixed cropping, crop rotation, conservation tillage, and cover cropping, can enhance
63 soil C and nutrient storage in tropical agroecosystems (Fahad et al. 2022). These practices are
64 characteristic of the shifting cultivation system (SCS).

65 Over 2.6 million km² of tropical land is subjected to SCS, making it the predominant farming
66 system in tropical regions (Heinimann et al. 2017). The SCS process involves clearing land
67 through slash-and-burn methods, cultivating it for a few years (typically 3–5 years), and then
68 leaving the land on fallow to naturally restore its fertility, while a new plot is cleared for cultivation
69 (Tripathi et al. 2017). The SCS has contributed to excessive rates of forest clearing (Cahyaningsih
70 et al. 2022; Olivetti et al. 2024), resulting in the significant release of soil C contributing to climate
71 change (CC) and land degradation (Amundson et al. 2015; Leon et al. 2022), both of which pose
72 serious threats to humanity. The SCS also leads to significant depletion of soil C and nutrient
73 stocks, with long-lasting consequences such as soil degradation, loss of biodiversity, carbon
74 emission, and decreased agricultural productivity, (Arunrat et al. 2024). As a result, a lengthy
75 fallow period is typically required for soil restoration. Unfortunately, the short fallow periods in
76 tropical regions do not allow for adequate recovery (Kozak and Pudelko 2021). Jalloh (2006)
77 reported that fallow durations have decreased to 5 years in rural areas and less than 4 years along
78 major highways. Mandah et al. (2024) reported a fallow duration of ≤ 3 years in rural communities.
79 Studies have shown that even a decade of fallow is insufficient for significant recovery of nutrient
80 loss after clearing and cultivation (Kintché et al. 2015; Almeida et al. 2017). Due to financial
81 constraints and lower education levels among farmers, farmers often rely on low-cost, suboptimal

82 practices to sustain their livelihoods (Souza et al. 2022). Addressing these issues requires a
83 combination of economic measures, subsidies, and support for agricultural innovation systems.

84 Although substantial information exists on the effects of indigenous agricultural management
85 practices (IAMPs) on soil C and nutrient dynamics in the SCS, this information is dispersed across
86 various studies and requires synthesis. Therefore, this review examines the existing findings,
87 controversies, and knowledge gaps regarding IAMPs in the SCS. It will be an invaluable tool for
88 guiding decision-making in the promotion of sustainable agriculture and in addressing climate
89 change adaptation and mitigation.

90 **2. Description of the shifting cultivation system (SCS)**

91 Worldwide, over 1 billion people practice the SCS, primarily in Africa, Asia, and Latin America,
92 where it has been a traditional practice in Indigenous communities for thousands of years
93 (Ramachandran 2023). However, the sustainability of SCS, especially in terms of conserving
94 tropical forest and savannah ecosystems, is increasingly threatened due to rapid population growth
95 and the rising demand for food (Borah et al. 2018; Edwards et al. 2019). The cycle of shifting
96 cultivation is summarized in Fig. 1.

97 Many IAMPs, such as deforestation, slash-and-burn, conventional tillage, and reduced fallow
98 periods, lead to significant and long-term depletion of soil C and nutrient stocks (Baul et al. 2023).
99 These effects are particularly critical in tropical countries like Indonesia and Malaysia (Mertz et
100 al. 2017), leading to the adoption of alternative land preparation methods, such as mulching,
101 improved forest conversion, mechanized land preparation, and the slash-and-char system (Tang
102 and Yap 2020). However, these alternatives have considerable financial costs (Souza et al. 2022).
103 As a result, farmers are often compelled to rely on low-cost management practices, such as slash-
104 and-burn and shortening fallow periods, to sustain subsistence farming (Ducourtieux 2005). Future
105 scientific recommendations and policymaking focused on promoting sustainable agriculture and
106 addressing climate change adaptation and mitigation should highlight the financial challenges
107 faced by these communities. Studies have categorized IAMPs in shifting cultivation into three
108 phases: conversion, cultivation, and restoration (Kleinman et al. 1995), as described in the
109 following sections.

110 **3. Management-induced effects in the different phases of the SCS**

111 **3.1 Conversion phase**

112 The main conversion trend has been from forest to agricultural lands, but with the demographic
113 rise, the conversion is now rapidly expanding to savannah areas.

114 **3.1.1 Conversion of forest to agricultural lands**

115 Deforestation is driven by growing food demand (Vos et al. 2019). Deforestation refers to
116 converting forests into agricultural land or other land uses (Hansen et al. 2013). Numerous studies

117 have quantified tropical forest loss in recent years, revealing trends, causes, and extent. In 2023,
118 the world lost 28.3 million hectares of tropical forest, with an average annual loss of 2.5 million
119 hectares (Pro et al. 2023). Shifting cultivation often results in high deforestation rates (Tripathi et
120 al. 2017). From 2000 to 2020, the tropics lost 16.6 million hectares of forest annually, with major
121 deforestation hotspots in the Amazon, Southeast Asia (especially Indonesia), and Central Africa
122 (especially the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC)) (Hansen et al. 2020). From 1990 to 2010,
123 Southeast Asia's forest cover decreased from 268 million hectares to 236 million hectares, with
124 annual loss rates of 0.67% (1990-2000) and 0.59% (2000-2010) (Stibig et al. 2013). Global Forest
125 Watch (GFW) 2021 provides real-time data on forest loss and degradation using satellite imagery.
126 According to their report for the year 2021, approximately 11 million hectares of tropical forest
127 were lost annually between the years 2019 and 2021. While there has been progress in
128 understanding these trends, significant knowledge gaps still exist regarding the impact of tropical
129 forest conversion on soil nutrients.

130 Haghverdi et al. (2020) found that forests store the highest levels of C compared to other land uses.
131 Forests are essential for C storage and climate change mitigation, holding 77% of the C in
132 vegetation and absorbing 2.6 billion tons annually, though 60% is released due to deforestation
133 (Ahmad et al. 2023). Forest ecosystems store 283 Gt of C in biomass, 38 Gt in dead wood, and
134 317 Gt in soils and litter indicating a total carbon content of forest ecosystems estimated at 638 Gt
135 for the year 2005 (Tebeje 2020). A study by Kassa et al. (2017) in Ethiopia found the highest SOC
136 stocks in forest soils, ranging from 320 to 412 Mg ha⁻¹. In Costa Rica, the amount of carbon in the
137 soil stayed about the same in both pastures and forests. However, after deforestation, around 50%
138 of the carbon originally from the forest in the top 40 cm of soil was lost over time (Huth et al.
139 2012). In Argentina's Semiarid Chaco Region, soil organic carbon dropped by 30% after 10 years
140 of farming, with the most significant loss in particulate organic carbon (Villarino et al. 2017).
141 Regarding the current rate of deforestation, the UN has set large-scale reforestation goals to restore
142 350 million hectares of degraded forests (Stanturf et al. 2019). From this perspective, emphasizing
143 agricultural practices like agroforestry, which has a high potential for SOC storage, is crucial. The
144 levels of SOC loss for various types of forest conversion are presented in Table 1.

145 The rate of deforestation in tropical areas for agricultural purposes from 2002 to 2019, measured
146 in million hectares (Fig. 2a), was obtained from the World Resources Institute (WRI 2021)
147 database. In a study by Kassa et al. (2017) on SOC loss during forest conversion to croplands, the
148 estimated average SOC loss was approximately 5.65 Mg ha⁻¹yr⁻¹. This allows for the estimation
149 of SOC loss in tropical areas used for agriculture between 2002 and 2019 (Fig. 2b).

150 Significant rates of agriculturally induced deforestation from the year 2002 to 2019, with
151 particularly critical situations in Brazil, Indonesia, and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC),
152 showed losses of 24.5, 9.47, and 8.33 million hectares, respectively (WRI 2021), (Fig. 2a).
153 Meanwhile, Fig. 2b highlights the severe loss of SOC in these countries, drawing the attention of

154 scientists, farmers, and policymakers to the urgent need for alternative solutions to address climate
155 change mitigation and adaptation.

156 Deforestation for pasture and plantation conversion significantly affects soil nutrient cycling and
157 availability. Studies in Costa Rica, Brazil, and Indonesia have shown that clearing forests reduces
158 soil N stocks and alters N dynamics (Huth et al. 2012; Allen et al. 2015). Kassa et al. (2017)
159 reported that N losses from forest conversion to croplands are like those from agroforestry to
160 croplands, with losses ranging from 0.3 to 1.1 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Awoonor et al. (2022) found a 47.77%
161 loss in N stocks due to forest-to-cropland conversion and a 20–45% reduction in available K.
162 Additionally, converting forests to tea farms led to significant declines in available K, from 341.31
163 ppm to 179.67 ppm, due to rapid organic matter mineralization and decreased microbial activity
164 (Gholoubi et al. 2019). Conversion of Brazilian forests to pastures and Eucalyptus plantations also
165 reduced N mineralization in upper soil layers, potentially increasing N limitations (López-Poma
166 et al. 2020). This may be due to decreased microbial biomass, which is closely linked to nitrogen
167 cycling rates (Allen et al. 2015).

168 Some studies on the effects of agriculturally induced deforestation show contradictory results
169 regarding soil C, N, P, and K storage. Mandah et al. (2024) reported that a study conducted in the
170 central region of Cameroon found no significant difference in soil C, N, P, and K content in a
171 change of land use from natural forest to agroforestry. Studies in Costa Rica, Turkey, and
172 Argentina have shown that converting forests to pastures or croplands generally decreases SOC
173 (Gülser et al. 2021). Kassa et al. (2017) found that deforestation for cropping led to a yearly
174 increase in P by 22 to 139%. A study on land use change from forest to tea fields showed no
175 significant impact on total N or available P (Gholoubi et al. 2019), suggesting that soil physical
176 indicators, such as bulk density and water-stable aggregates, might explain the stability of these
177 nutrients. Soils with lower bulk density (less compact) have more pore space, which improves
178 water infiltration and root growth enabling better nutrient availability (Lampurlanés and Cantero-
179 Martínez 2003). On the other hand aggregates form when organic matter binds soil particles
180 together, creating a more stable structure (Dalal and Bridge 2020). However, knowledge gaps
181 persist, particularly regarding the effects of forest type and cultivation stage on soil carbon changes
182 (Thomaz et al. 2020).

183 **3.1.2 Conversion of savannah to agricultural lands**

184 Forest areas are progressively shifting, giving way to savannahs because of climatic changes (Sales
185 et al. 2020). Savannahs account for about 20% of global soil C stocks (FAOSTAT 2009). The
186 impact of land-use changes on SOC stocks depends heavily on biophysical factors such as
187 precipitation and soil clay mineralogy (Powers et al. 2011). Chadwick et al. (2023) reported a 15-
188 25% decrease in SOC stocks within the first five years after conversion, mainly due to the removal
189 of deep-rooted perennial vegetation and increased soil disturbance. A study that focused on the
190 conversion of tropical savannah ecosystems in Sub-Saharan Africa to agriculture, primarily maize
191 and soybean cultivation showed a significant reduction in nutrients in the top 20 cm of soil,

192 primarily due to soil disturbance, removal of biomass, and changes in microbial activity (Barros
193 et al. 2022). The results indicated a decrease of 40% SOC, 40% N, 40% P, and 35% K. Findings
194 in Brazil on the conversion of tropical savannahs to pastureland led to significant declines in SOC
195 in the top 30 cm of soil. The study reported a decrease of 25-35% SOC, 25-30% N, 25-30% P, and
196 20-30% K (Silva et al. 2021). Hergoualc'h et al. (2020), also investigated the conversion of tropical
197 savannahs to oil palm plantations in Southeast Asia. The results indicate a substantial decline in
198 soil organic C, with losses of 30-50% SOC, 50% N, 40% P, and 40% K in the top 15 cm of soil.
199 The decrease is attributed to intensive land use, changes in soil structure, and reduced organic
200 matter input after conversion. While these studies provide valuable insights into the effects of
201 savannah conversion to croplands, caution is to be taken when extrapolating results to different
202 tropical regions because land-use transitions vary depending on biophysical factors like
203 precipitation and clay mineralogy, making field observations unrepresentative of most tropical
204 landscapes (Powers et al. 2011).

205 **3.1.3 Slash-and-burn**

206 Slash-and-burn practice prevails in the SCS, where native vegetation is felled, dried, and burned,
207 typically during the dry season (Tang et al. 2020). The land is cultivated until yields decline,
208 indicating a loss of fertility, which prompts farmers to move to new areas. This practice contributes
209 to the loss of C, N, P, and K leading to deforestation, soil degradation, and C emissions (Santos et
210 al. 2020; Taufik et al. 2021). Numerous studies have highlighted the negative effects of slash-and-
211 burn on soil C and nutrient levels. Taufik et al. (2021) observed significant losses in tropical forests
212 in Southeast Asia, including 30-40% of SOC, 25-40% of N, 20-30% of P, and 20-30% of K in the
213 top 20 cm of soil. Similarly, in the Amazon, slash-and-burn resulted in a 35% loss of SOC, 35%
214 of N, 30-40% of P, and 25-35% of K (Santos et al. 2020). Southeast Asian forests are facing severe
215 threats due to deforestation and changes in land use, leading to significant C losses and
216 environmental damage. From 2000 to 2020, the region lost approximately 0.5% of its forest cover
217 each year. As a result, C stocks in natural forests are expected to decrease from 19.7 PgC in 2000
218 to 15.7 PgC by 2030 (Sasaki et al. 2021). The loss of forests causes unprecedented annual C losses
219 of 424 Tg C per year (Feng et al. 2021). Van et al. (2020) highlighted similar reductions in the
220 Congo Basin, with 40% SOC, 40% N, and 25-40% P losses. The negative and beneficial impacts
221 of slash-and-burn are illustrated in Fig. 3.

222 While some studies report negative impacts on soil carbon and nutrients (Baul et al. 2023), others
223 suggest limited detrimental effects (Mukul et al. 2022). Studies have shown that slash-and-burn
224 can be beneficial in certain situations. Shifting cultivation relies on nutrient inputs from biomass
225 burning, particularly P, which is often a limiting factor in tropical systems (Mahajan et al. 2020;
226 Wapongnungsang et al. 2021). This practice provides a quick and cost-effective method for
227 clearing large areas of vegetation (Yadav 2013). It remains viable in areas with limited access to
228 modern farming technologies or financial resources (Rammohan et al. 2021). Slash-and-burn can
229 create a fertile layer for a few years, although fertility eventually declines (Zwartendijk et al. 2020).

230 Nutrients from slash-and-burn are typically available for uptake only during the first cycle of SCS,
231 with higher availability during warmer periods. However, the positive effects of slash-and-burn on
232 soil quality are temporary, highlighting the need for long-term alternative solutions to ensure
233 agricultural sustainability and support climate change adaptation and mitigation.

234 **3.2 Cultivation phase**

235 **3.2.1 Tillage**

236 Tillage is a significant agricultural practice in tropical and subtropical regions, particularly in
237 Southeast Asia, where it is widely used for land preparation despite its potential long-term negative
238 impacts on soil health (Li et al. 2024). Conventional tillage disrupts soil structure, leading to the
239 breakdown of aggregates, compaction, and disturbance of soil communities, which results in
240 substantial losses of C, N, P, and K, especially in the top 10 cm of soil, reducing crop yields
241 (D'Haene et al. 2008). Liu et al. (2020) found that conventional tillage reduces SOC by 15-30%
242 and N by 15-18%, mainly due to increased microbial decomposition and reduced organic matter
243 retention. In contrast, minimum tillage has been shown to positively affect the concentrations of
244 SOC, N, P, and K. A study reported potential yearly gains of 20 kg C, 60 kg N, 9 kg P, and 17 kg
245 K, alongside higher grain yields (Yadav et al. 2019). Yadav et al. (2021) further reported higher
246 available N, P, K, and 18.6-31.4% higher soil moisture content after rainy season maize under
247 minimum tillage compared to conventional tillage. These benefits are attributed to increased
248 microbial biomass and enhanced N mineralization (Spargo et al. 2011).

249 Many studies have highlighted the benefits of minimum tillage on soil quality. It reduces
250 disturbance to soil organisms, preserves soil fertility, promotes macro-porosity, and enhances
251 water retention (Murugan et al. 2014). Minimum tillage also regulates nutrient supply to crops by
252 controlling the rate of mineralization and immobilization through microbial activity (Behzad and
253 Ahmad 2014). Zhang et al. (2021) found that, over 10 years, minimum tillage increased SOC by
254 20%, N by 15-20%, and P by 10-20% compared to conventional tillage. Another study reported a
255 25% increase in SOC and an 8-12% increase in N. Li et al. (2021) showed that no-tillage increased
256 N availability by 10-15% due to better organic matter preservation and reduced N leaching, along
257 with a 10-20% increase in K (K). Long-term crop rotation under no-tillage or minimum tillage in
258 Brazil enhanced the mineralization of organic P species, leading to re-adsorption in non-labile
259 forms (Rigon et al. 2024). Additionally, minimum tillage combined with cover crops and legumes
260 is more effective for soil C and nutrient storage, as legumes improve soil fertility and diversify
261 cropping systems (Ojiem et al. 2014). Long-term experiments and modeling approaches are
262 needed to further understand SOC and nutrient dynamics under tillage in tropical SCS (Naresh et
263 al. 2017).

264 **3.2.2 Mixed cropping rotation**

265 Mixed cropping and crop rotation are considered more sustainable agricultural practices than
266 monocropping, which is detrimental to soil health (Alemayehu et al. 2020; Hashakimana et al.
267 2023). Many farmers practicing sustainable cropping systems use mixed cropping rotations. Mixed
268 cropping, also known as polyculture, involves growing multiple crops on the same land (Plucknett
269 and Smith, 1986), while crop rotation involves planting different crops sequentially (Higgs et al.
270 1990). These practices promote crop diversity and a balanced diet, and research shows that mixed
271 cropping improves soil structure (Raimbault and Vyn 1991), as well as soil C and nutrient storage
272 (Campbell and Zentner, 1993), especially when combined with conservation tillage. Crop
273 rotational diversity has been shown to influence soil microbial communities and increase disease
274 suppressive capacity (Peralta et al. 2018).

275 Data on the impact of mixed cropping rotation on soil C and nutrients in tropical regions is limited.
276 However, Li et al. (2024) reported that mixed cropping combined with crop residue incorporation
277 significantly boosted SOC, improving soil structure and fertility. Similarly, a study in northwest
278 Ethiopia found that SOC, N, P, and K increased by 67%, 89%, 150%, and 44%, respectively, over
279 three years with mixed cropping (Alemayehu et al. 2020). In temperate climates, studies on wheat-
280 maize rotation and mixed cropping show that legume-based systems enhance SOC, N, P, and K
281 by promoting N fixation and root biomass, leading to greater SOC compared to monocropping
282 (Zhang et al. 2022). Thus, legume-based mixed crop rotations are recommended for their N
283 fixation benefits, suggesting that IAMPs could promote sustainability in tropical SCS. However,
284 long-term studies are needed to further explore the positive effects of these systems on soil
285 properties and nutrient dynamics.

286 **3.2.3 Agroforestry**

287 Carvalho et al. (2023) have shown that agroforestry could be a promising solution to improve soil
288 health and productivity in SCSs. Research has shown that agroforestry can enhance soil nutrient
289 availability, with notable annual increases in SOC by 21%, N by 13%, and P by 11% (Muchane et
290 al. 2020). Additionally, Agroforestry systems in Indonesia have proven to be highly effective in
291 enhancing soil C storage and providing ecosystem services, particularly when compared to
292 conventional farming practices. Research indicates that agroforestry can sequester up to 50% more
293 C than monoculture systems. For example, cacao-based agroforestry has been shown to store C at
294 levels ranging from 75 to 89 Mg ha⁻¹ (Sari et al. 2020). In West Java, mixed-tree agroforestry
295 systems achieved C stocks of 108.9 Mg ha⁻¹ (Siarudin et al. 2021). Additionally, agroforestry
296 practices have been found to increase SOC by 21% and N storage by 13% compared to
297 monocultural cropping systems (Muchane et al. 2020). In the semi-arid regions of Indonesia,
298 agroforestry systems demonstrated SOC levels 5% higher than those of other land uses, which
299 were below 1% (Melinda and Takalapeta, 2021). In the drylands of eastern Kenya, agroforestry
300 woodlots demonstrated higher SOC and N levels than parklands and grazing lands (Mutuku et al.
301 2021). Similarly, in northwestern Ethiopia, converting land to a teff-Acacia agroforestry system

302 resulted in a 21 Mg C ha⁻¹ increase in SOC stocks per year over 12 years (Kim et al. 2022). Studies
303 in Indonesia (Sattler et al. 2022) and Ethiopia (Kassa et al. 2017) further highlight agroforestry's
304 significant role in improving soil C storage. Mandah et al. (2024) in a study on the variability of
305 SOC and nutrient content across land uses and agriculturally induced land use changes in a forest-
306 savanna transition benchmark showed that agroforestry can enhance the ecological resilience of
307 lands affected by land-use changes. Cardoso et al. (2006) reported that leguminous trees in
308 agroforestry systems are crucial for N fixation. Additionally, agroforestry supports biodiversity
309 preservation improving nutrient dynamics in ecosystems (Keesstra et al. 2018). Agroforestry also
310 reduces soil erosion by up to 50% and enhances soil texture and stability (Muchane et al. 2020;
311 Ngaba et al. 2024). These findings show the potential of agroforestry as a sustainable agricultural
312 approach that can contribute significantly to climate change mitigation, biodiversity conservation,
313 and improved soil health in tropical regions. However, Prolonged periods of experimentation (≥ 3
314 years) are needed to show quantitative evidence of the long-term effects of agroforestry and the
315 overall benefits of intercropped trees on soil C and nutrient storage and ecosystem functioning.
316 Additionally, the dynamics of P depletion in agroforestry systems are hardly addressed (Mertz et
317 al. 2021).

318 **3.2.4 Cover cropping**

319 Cover crops, especially during fallow periods, are commonly used to prevent nutrient loss from
320 agricultural fields (De Baets et al. 2011). Hartwig and Ammon (2002) defined cover crops as
321 ground cover sown before, during, or after a crop, and removed before planting the next crop. This
322 traditional practice is increasingly recognized for its potential in promoting sustainable agriculture
323 and supporting ecosystem services (Khan et al. 2021). Cover crops provide several benefits,
324 including improving soil and water quality. A meta-analysis found that cover crops increased SOC
325 by an average of 15.5%, with larger increases in fine-textured soils and temperate climates (Jian
326 et al. 2020). Mixed cover crops with legumes are particularly effective. They enhance P
327 availability, regulate N levels (Haruna and Nkongolo 2020), and maintain soil C and N by
328 sequestering them from the atmosphere, reducing losses, and increasing N availability for
329 subsequent crops (Drinkwater et al. 2007), which in turn boosts yields (Wittwer et al. 2017). Cover
330 crops also suppress weeds by competing for light, water, and nutrients (Cordeau et al. 2015),
331 protect soil from erosion, and reduce nutrient loss from leaching and runoff (Khan et al. 2021). In
332 addition, legume-based cover crops enhance soil structure by increasing soil organic matter (SOM)
333 and total nitrogen, which in turn improves nutrient availability. Creeping cover crops provide
334 better soil coverage and more effective weed suppression than upright crops (Khan et al. 2021).

335 A review of 106 studies across 372 sites in various countries and climatic zones showed that cover
336 crops significantly reduced N leaching and increased SOC sequestration (Abdella et al. 2019).
337 Studies indicate that the positive impact of cover crops on soil C is closely linked to the additional
338 aboveground and belowground biomass, as well as crop residues entering the soil (Palese et al.
339 2014). Biomass yield for different cover crops varies, with legumes yielding 3.3 to 9.8 Mg ha⁻¹

340 (Hubbard et al. 2013), corn 2 to 12 Mg ha⁻¹ (Schmer et al. 2014), small grain systems 1.5 to 7 Mg
341 ha⁻¹ (Malhi and Lemke 2013), and grasses 0.56 to 5.03 Mg ha⁻¹ (Sainju et al. 2017). Legumes tend
342 to have the highest biomass yield and are more effective in storing SOC and nutrients. However,
343 further experiments are needed to confirm these findings. Cover crops can also impact soil
344 nutrients, such as increasing P availability and reducing ammonium levels (Haruna and Nkongolo
345 2020). Additionally, many studies focus on the amount of SOC sequestered by cover crops without
346 addressing changes in SOC stocks (Ghimire et al. 2019). Six years are needed to assess the effects
347 of cover crops on SOC stocks (Poeplau et al. 2015), longer-term experiments are necessary to
348 provide conclusive evidence.

349 A major gap is the lack of long-term studies on cover crops' effects on soil properties (Haruna et
350 al. 2020), with many previous studies neglecting key factors such as crop species, soil type, tillage
351 intensity, planting period, residue quality and quantity, and climate. However, a study reported a
352 gain of 6-10 kg⁻¹ ha⁻¹ of N from oat cover crops in sandy/loamy soil, under an arid/semi-arid
353 climate (González et al. 2023). A study also showed inconsistent results; from a five-year
354 experiment in Nebraska that showed no significant effect on bulk SOC, though changes in water-
355 extractable organic matter and particulate organic matter composition were observed (Anuo et al.
356 2023).

357 **3.2.5 Crop residue incorporation**

358 Crop residue management plays an important role in improving soil C and fertility (Sarkar et al.
359 2020). Residues, including stalks, stubble, leaves, roots, and seed pods, enhance soil structure by
360 promoting aggregate stability (Khan et al. 2021), reducing soil erosion from wind (Blanco -
361 Canqui et al. 2017) and water (Kenney et al. 2015), and ultimately boosting soil quality and
362 productivity. Legume crop residues, which produce more biomass than cereals, are rich in N and
363 promote rapid mineralization (Tiemann et al. 2015). In contrast, cereal residues, with higher C-to-
364 N (C: N) ratios, may need additional N fertilizer for decomposition (Wang et al. 2004). Retaining
365 crop residues has positive effects on SOC and crop yields. Studies show that residue retention can
366 increase SOC by 12-37% compared to removal (Li et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2020), particularly in
367 topsoil and warmer regions (Alvarez 2024). When combined with minimal tillage, such as no-till
368 or reduced tillage, SOC stocks can increase by 27-29% compared to conventional tillage (Li et al.
369 2019). Additionally, residue retention improves soil structure, water retention, and nutrient
370 availability (Wang et al. 2020). Incorporating crop residues has been shown to increase maize
371 grain yields (Uzoh et al. 2019), and different crops contribute varying levels of C, N, P, and K,
372 with cotton producing the most C and rice the most P (Fu et al. 2021). Studies by Ruis and Blanco-
373 Canqui (2017) revealed that removing over 50% of crop residues decreases SOC stocks by 0.87
374 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ while removing less than 50% results in a smaller decrease of 0.31 Mg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.

375 Some studies, however, have controversially reported that incorporating crop residues can have
376 negative or no impact. crop residues may interfere with crop growth and cause phytotoxicity in
377 seedlings, particularly in cereals such as wheat (Elliott et al. 1978). Additionally, residue retention

378 may increase greenhouse gas emissions, particularly in the short term (Wang et al. 2020). The
379 benefits of residue retention on SOC and crop yields are most noticeable in double-cropping
380 systems and with long-term management (Li et al. 2019; Li et al. 2020). Residues around seeds
381 can reduce seed-to-soil contact by increasing macro porosity, which negatively affects crop growth
382 (Brown et al. 1996). Khan et al. (2021) stated that crop residue incorporation did not impact soil P
383 and C. Future research works in this area should consider the effects of factors such as residue
384 quantity and quality, soil type, tillage practices, and climate conditions for more reliable
385 conclusions.

386 Crop residue removal can significantly affect SOC and soil health. A meta-analysis found that
387 residue harvest decreased topsoil SOC by 11%, with more pronounced effects in warmer regions
388 and soils with low SOC (Alvarez, 2024). Excessive crop residue removal can negatively impact
389 soil properties and crop productivity. It reduces soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks, with an average
390 decrease of 11% in topsoil (Alvarez 2024). It also deprives microbes of fresh C sources, forcing
391 them to use older, less efficient ones, which further depletes SOC (Ruis et al. 2017). This practice
392 negatively affects the soil's physical, chemical, and biological properties, leading to more erosion
393 and reduced water infiltration (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2009). However, cover crops can help
394 offset these negative effects on SOC and soil properties (Ruis and Blanco-Canqui 2017). To reduce
395 these impacts, residue removal guidelines should consider soil type, and best management
396 practices such as cover crops and crop rotations should be adopted (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2009).

397 **3.3 Restoration phase**

398 Fallow is an ancient and cost-effective land management technique for recovering soil nutrients
399 (Costantini et al. 2016). The sustainability of SCS depends on maintaining longer fallow periods
400 (Filho et al. 2015). During the fallow phase, soil properties, such as organic matter, nutrient
401 cycling, and microbial activity, improve (Funakawa et al. 2006). The length of the fallow period
402 is largely influenced by population size (Gockowski et al. 2004). Recent data about fallow duration
403 and the impact on soil nutrients is still very scarce. However, the following sections discuss the
404 effects of both prolonged and shortened fallow periods on soil C and nutrient levels.

405 **3.3.1 Prolonged fallow**

406 Studies have shown that prolonged fallow periods of 20 years or more generally result in higher
407 levels of C, N, P, and K in the soil (Aguilera et al. 2013). Longer fallows help maintain soil fertility
408 and biodiversity (Wood et al. 2017). Longer fallows also enhance the availability of P, especially
409 in natural systems, and positively correlate with P uptake in crops (Kolawole et al. 2005). In sandy
410 paddy fields, fallow periods can increase N and the C/N ratio (Sun et al. 2022). Miranda et al.
411 (2009) found significant increases in SOC and soil nutrients (N, P, and K) after 7 years of fallow.
412 Prolonged fallowing also reduces runoff (36%), soil loss (65%), and soil C loss (81%) compared
413 to cultivated lands (Temjen et al. 2022). While long-term fallow improves soil C sequestration and
414 nutrient content, invasive species like goldenrod can cause soil degradation (Kozak and Pudełko,
415 2021). Overall, fallowing is an effective practice for restoring soil fertility and nutrient availability.

416 Some research on soil properties in tropical fallow systems has shown mixed results. Some studies
417 report no significant improvements in soil properties with longer fallow periods in high tropical
418 areas (Abreu et al. 2009). Similarly, Masse et al. (2004) observed no recovery of SOM and
419 nutrients in sandy soils after 4 years of fallow in Senegal. Gomez-Montano et al. (2013) noted that
420 longer fallow periods reduced soil fungal diversity and decreased bacterial diversity in croplands.
421 These findings suggest that more research is needed, particularly considering factors such as soil
422 type, fallow type, and climate to draw definitive conclusions.

423 **3.3.2 Shortened fallow length.**

424 Short fallow cycles, combined with changing climatic conditions, can threaten soil health and
425 exacerbate the negative impacts on soil characteristics (Lalthakimi et al. 2023). Evidence shows
426 that fallow periods have decreased from the recommended 10 years or more (Cousteaux et al. 2008)
427 to about 5 years in rural areas and 3-4 years along major highways (Jalloh 2006; Kamara et al.
428 2016). Meanwhile, cropping practices often lead to a depletion of soil C, nitrogen N, phosphorus
429 P, and other essential nutrients, significantly impacting soil fertility (Aguilera et al. 2013).
430 However, there is limited information on the extent of reduction in fallow periods (Ando et al.
431 2014). Shortened fallow periods limit vegetation regrowth, reducing the input of C and essential
432 nutrients (N, P, and K) required for soil fertility restoration (Motavalli et al. 2009), however, they
433 play a crucial role in nutrient cycling and soil carbon dynamics in shifting cultivation systems
434 (SCSs).

435 **4. Future Perspectives**

436 Research on soil C, N, P, and K content in tropical SCSs faces several challenges, including
437 nutrient depletion, climate change, and the need for long-term monitoring. Recent studies, such as
438 those by Sattler et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2024), focus on understanding how land conversion
439 affects C dynamics, emphasizing the need for more longitudinal data on soil C storage. Farmers
440 often rely on fallow periods to restore soil fertility, but these periods are shrinking due to
441 population pressure. Research by Mertz et al. (2021) and Camargo et al. (2023) shows that fallow
442 periods are insufficient for replenishing critical nutrients like P, highlighting the need for new
443 management strategies. Indigenous soil management practices, as discussed by Gupta et al. (2023),
444 are often not validated using modern scientific methods, limiting their broader application. Li et
445 al. (2022) emphasize the importance of establishing long-term monitoring stations in tropical
446 shifting cultivation areas to assess the effectiveness of soil management practices. A study by
447 Keesstra et al. (2024) further highlights how climate change accelerates soil degradation, leading
448 to greater nutrient and C loss, which underscores the need for climate-resilient management
449 practices.

450 Lefebvre et al. (2019) note considerable variability in tropical soils, with distinct soil types,
451 nutrient profiles, and moisture levels across regions, complicating the development of generalized
452 management strategies. Moreover, factors influencing SOC and nutrient availability including
453 fallow age, patch size, and slope are hardly addressed (Mukul et al. 2022). Future research should

454 address local soil characteristics when formulating management recommendations. There is also
455 a growing call to integrate Indigenous agricultural knowledge with modern scientific approaches
456 to develop more sustainable soil management practices (Gupta et al. 2023). Future studies should
457 explore the potential synergy between indigenous and contemporary techniques. However,
458 Mandah et al. (2024) reveal limited information on intercropped trees' economic and
459 environmental benefits. Finally, future research should focus on harmonizing measurement units
460 to improve the comparison and understanding of research findings across studies. In addition,
461 recent studies suggest that cropping history may be more influential than fallow duration in long-
462 term soil and vegetation dynamics (Wood et al. 2017). Therefore, sustainable management of
463 croplands through other good management options should rather be promoted to ensure an increase
464 in food supply considering the fast-increasing rate of the population.

465 In summary, nutrient dynamics vary in the SCS, with some studies showing higher C and nutrient
466 stocks in shifting cultivation sites (Baul et al. 2023), while others found higher nutrient content in
467 younger fallows (Mukul et al. 2022). Another study reported that SCS results in less carbon loss
468 from soil profiles compared to intensive cultivation (Lal and Logan 2018). These studies further
469 reported that nutrient levels may increase (Baul et al. 2023) or remain stable (Mukul et al. 2022)
470 under shifting cultivation implying that shifting cultivation may not be as detrimental to soil
471 quality as previously assumed, highlighting the need for further research in this area. The research
472 gaps described in this section reflect the complexity of managing soil C and nutrients in tropical
473 SCSs. Overcoming them will require long-term, interdisciplinary research that combines
474 indigenous knowledge with modern science, along with improved data collection and policy
475 support to ensure sustainability in these systems.

476 **Conclusion**

477 The tropical SCSs encompass both detrimental and beneficial agricultural practices. Poor
478 practices, such as deforestation, slash-and-burn techniques, shortening fallow periods, and
479 conventional tillage, driven by the increasing demand for food, contribute to soil C and nutrient
480 depletion, ultimately reducing crop yields. Addressing these challenges requires balancing food
481 security with sustainable agriculture, climate change adaptation, and mitigation. To promote long-
482 term agricultural sustainability, policies should encourage the adoption of good practices such as
483 agroforestry, mixed cropping, crop rotation, cover cropping, reduced tillage, and crop residue
484 incorporation. Overall, the research suggests that shifting cultivation may not be as detrimental to
485 soil quality as previously thought, particularly when longer fallow periods are employed. The main
486 challenge lies in the adoption of these good agricultural practices which are often accompanied by
487 cost posing a barrier for smallholder farmers. As such, in addition to educating farmers about
488 sustainable practices, there is a critical need for state-supported financial incentives, both for
489 farmers and the research community. This support will facilitate the transition to more sustainable
490 practices and encourage necessary research to improve the effectiveness of these techniques. By
491 aligning these efforts with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs),
492 particularly SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land), we can

493 ensure that the tropical SCSs contribute to long-term food security while preserving environmental
494 health and supporting resilient agricultural systems.

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999

1000 **Table 1. Effects of forest conversion to agricultural lands on soil organic carbon (SOC) loss**

Direction of conversion	SOC loss (%)	References	Country
Forest to cropland	50 %	Menezes et al. (2021)	NE Brazil,
Forest to cropland	4 %	Smith et al. (2024)	Virginia
Forest to cropland	28%	Yang et al. (2019)	China
Forest to cropland	50.8 %	Awoonor et al. (2021)	Ghana
Forest to cropland	60 %	Gonzalez et al. (2023)	Spain
Forest to cropland	40 – 60 %	Cardoso et al. (2020)	Brazil
Forest to cropland	50 %	Favier et al. (2022)	New Caledonia
Forest to cropland	25 %	Möller et al. (2022)	Germany
Forest to cropland	30-40 %	Ndiaye et al. (2021)	Senegal
Forest to cropland	3.8 %	Li et al. (2022)	China, Myanmar, Laos, Thailand, Cambodia, Vietnam
Forest to cropland	50%	Ordoñez et al. (2023)	Mexico

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1002

1003 **Figures**

1004

1005 **Fig. 1.**

1006 Shifting cultivation cycle and its positive and negative effects, adapted from Yemefack et al.
1007 (2006), and Mbogba et al. (2015)

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1009

1010 **Fig. 2**

1011 Estimated tropical primary forest loss (a) and SOC loss due to the conversion of tropical forests
 1012 to croplands (b) for agricultural purposes from the year 2002 to 2019, adapted from WRI (2021)
 1013 and Kassa et al. (2017).

1014 PNG: Papua New Guinea, DRC: Democratic Republic of Congo, Tg: Teragram

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1016

1017 **Fig. 3**

1018 Positive and negative effects of the slash-and-burn practice on agriculture and climate in the
 1019 shifting cultivation and alternative solutions.